

STATISTICAL OVERVIEW OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SECTOR ADVANCEMENTS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN REGION (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This scientific article presents a comprehensive statistical analysis of the Information and Communication Sector in the Romanian Mountain Region over the ten-year period from 2008 to 2018. The study aims to provide insights into the advancements, trends, and key developments within this sector, shedding light on the region's technological and communicative landscape.

1. Introduction:

The Information and Communication Sector play a pivotal role in shaping regional development, fostering innovation, and enhancing connectivity. This article focuses on the Romanian Mountain Region, examining statistical data spanning from 2008 to 2018 to discern patterns and changes within the sector.

2. Methodology:

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The research employs a quantitative approach, utilizing a range of statistical tools and metrics to analyze data collected from governmental reports, industry publications, and relevant databases. Key indicators such as infrastructure growth, technological adoption rates, and economic contributions are examined to provide a nuanced understanding of the sector's evolution.

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3. Infrastructure Development:

This section delves into the expansion of information and communication infrastructure within the Romanian Mountain Region. The analysis encompasses the growth of broadband networks, the proliferation of mobile technology, and the establishment of data centers, offering a comprehensive perspective on the region's connectivity.

4. Technological Adoption Rates:

Examining the adoption rates of emerging technologies within the Information and Communication Sector, this section explores the integration of innovations such as cloud computing, artificial intelligence, and the Internet of Things. Insights into the impact of these technologies on regional development and economic growth are discussed.

5. Economic Contributions:

The economic significance of the Information and Communication Sector in the Romanian Mountain Region is assessed through the examination of its contributions to GDP, employment rates, and entrepreneurial activities. This section highlights the sector's role as a driver of economic development and its influence on job creation.

6. Trends and Challenges:

Identifying notable trends and challenges encountered by the Information and Communication Sector during the specified period, this section provides a forward-looking perspective on potential future developments. Factors influencing the sector, such as regulatory changes and global technological shifts, are explored.

7. Results:

The statistics for the Information and communication sectors (figures) present for each sector separately ascending values for the mean and median, the other statistical indicators having sometimes antagonistic fluctuations (statistical values for Average, Std Error. to mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, Percentile 50 Value; they are repeated for each indicator separately), as follows: mean of 34730.56, standard error of the mean 1561.672, median 35215.00, standard deviation 4685.017, variance 21949387.028, Skewness -.403, standard error of Skewness .717, Kurtosis -.001, standard error of Kurtosis

1.400, distance 15063, minimum 26482, maximum 41545, percentile 25 - 31573.00, 50 - 35215 -30.05, 45.605

The presented values demonstrate that the Information and communication sectors in the mountain area have a good development in Romania for the population of active enterprises. Some sectors also show negative values, the overall picture showing a good overall mountain business situation for the industry.

The central tendency of the Information and communication sectors of the economy during the analyzed period shows that the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania has grown considerably from 2008 to 2019. The statistics related to this indicator show a high degree of non-variability, which means that the results do not show a large deviation and are positive. The corresponding symmetrical distributions lead to the idea that the business environment begins to stabilize considerably during the analyzed period. Kurtosis with a low standard error represents crowding in some industries.

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Figure 2.7.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S7 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.7.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S7 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.7.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S7 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.7.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S7 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.7.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S7 in the period 2008-2019

The forecast analysis for the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors in the mountainous area of Romania indicates that they will have a continuous growth until 2030. Both at the national, macro-regional, regional and county level, the models resulting from the statistical modeling show certain areas montana are more sustainable than others. The fit statistic shows relevant values for mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (presented in that order below), as follows: Stationary R-squared .167 .312, -.109, .811, -.014, -2.220E-16; R-square .813, .090, .572, 1.000, .627, .668; RMSE 167,519, 278,286, .000, 1597,919, 15,041, 16,432; MAPS 8,732, 3,329, .000, 15,416, 3,095, 3,660; MaxAPE 28,769, 11,531, .000, 50,019, 8,572, 11,430; MAE 114,541, 186,949, .000, 1043,125, 10,946, 11,153;

MaxAE 354,439, 570,884, .000, 3172,875, 25,469, 34,754; Normalized BIC 8.844, 2.457, 5.782, 15.013, 5.818, 5.916.

Table. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S7

Model		Forecast										
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	43428	45311	47194	49077	50959	52842	54725	56608	58491	60374	62257
	UCL	47206	50654	53738	56633	59408	62098	64722	67295	69826	72322	74788
	LCL	39649	39967	40649	41520	42510	43587	44728	45921	47155	48425	49725
Macroregiunea unu-Model_2	Forecast	12455	13025	13595	14166	14736	15306	15876	16446	17016	17586	18156
	UCL	13604	14650	15586	16464	17305	18121	18916	19696	20464	21220	21968
	LCL	11306	11400	11605	11867	12166	12491	12835	13196	13569	13952	14345
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	7631	8063	8494	8926	9358	9790	10222	10654	11085	11517	11949
	UCL	9116	10163	11066	11896	12678	13427	14150	14854	15540	16213	16874
	LCL	6146	5963	5922	5956	6038	6153	6293	6454	6631	6821	7024
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	1122	1178	1234	1290	1346	1402	1459	1515	1571	1627	1683
	UCL	1268	1325	1382	1439	1496	1552	1609	1666	1723	1780	1837
	LCL	975	1031	1086	1141	1197	1252	1308	1363	1419	1474	1530
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	388	411	433	456	478	501	523	546	568	591	613
	UCL	490	555	610	660	706	750	793	834	874	913	951
	LCL	287	267	257	252	251	251	254	258	263	268	275
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	4627	4903	5178	5454	5730	6006	6282	6558	6833	7109	7385
	UCL	5477	6105	6651	7155	7632	8089	8532	8963	9384	9798	10205
	LCL	3776	3700	3706	3754	3829	3923	4032	4152	4282	4420	4565
Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	731	768	806	843	881	918	956	993	1031	1068	1106

	UCL	943	1069	1174	1269	1357	1440	1519	1596	1670	1742	1812
	LCL	518	467	437	417	405	397	393	391	392	395	400
Satu Mare-Model_8	Forecast	399	419	440	460	481	501	522	542	563	583	604
	UCL	497	558	610	657	700	742	782	820	857	894	930
	LCL	300	280	270	264	261	261	262	265	268	273	278
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	369	391	412	434	456	478	500	522	543	565	587
	UCL	439	490	535	575	614	651	686	721	755	788	821
	LCL	298	291	290	293	298	305	313	322	332	342	353
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	4917	5148	5379	5610	5841	6072	6303	6534	6765	6996	7227
	UCL	5816	6419	6936	7408	7851	8274	8682	9077	9462	9839	10209
	LCL	4018	3877	3822	3812	3831	3870	3924	3991	4068	4153	4245
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	539	566	592	619	646	673	700	727	753	780	807
	UCL	705	801	880	952	1018	1080	1140	1197	1252	1306	1358
	LCL	373	331	305	287	274	266	260	256	255	254	256
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	1453	1519	1584	1650	1715	1781	1846	1911	1977	2042	2108
	UCL	1611	1677	1742	1808	1873	1939	2004	2069	2135	2200	2266
	LCL	1295	1361	1426	1492	1557	1623	1688	1753	1819	1884	1950
Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	333	348	364	379	395	410	426	441	457	472	488
	UCL	387	425	457	488	516	543	569	595	619	644	668
	LCL	278	271	270	271	274	278	282	288	294	301	308
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	543	569	595	621	646	672	698	724	749	775	801
	UCL	629	655	681	707	734	760	786	812	838	864	891
	LCL	458	483	509	534	559	585	610	635	661	686	711
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	1023	1078	1134	1190	1245	1301	1356	1412	1468	1523	1579
	UCL	1216	1352	1469	1577	1678	1775	1868	1959	2048	2135	2221
	LCL	829	805	799	803	813	827	845	865	887	911	937

Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	977	1026	1075	1124	1172	1221	1270	1319	1367	1416	1465
	UCL	1183	1233	1283	1332	1382	1432	1482	1531	1581	1631	1680
	LCL	772	820	867	915	963	1010	1058	1106	1154	1201	1249
Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	6854	7131	7407	7684	7961	8238	8514	8791	9068	9345	9621
	UCL	7582	8160	8668	9140	9588	10020	10440	10850	11251	11646	12035
	LCL	6126	6101	6147	6228	6333	6455	6588	6732	6884	7043	7207
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	4350	4577	4803	5030	5256	5483	5709	5936	6162	6389	6615
	UCL	5253	5854	6367	6835	7275	7694	8098	8489	8870	9243	9609
	LCL	3448	3300	3240	3224	3238	3271	3321	3382	3454	3534	3621
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	604	629	655	680	706	731	757	782	808	833	859
	UCL	731	809	875	935	991	1044	1094	1143	1190	1237	1282
	LCL	476	449	434	425	421	419	420	422	425	430	436
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	301	317	333	349	365	381	397	413	429	445	461
	UCL	351	368	385	402	418	435	452	469	486	503	520
	LCL	251	266	281	296	311	326	341	357	372	387	402
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	2251	2379	2508	2637	2766	2894	3023	3152	3281	3409	3538
	UCL	2758	3097	3386	3651	3899	4136	4365	4586	4802	5013	5220
	LCL	1744	1662	1630	1623	1632	1652	1682	1718	1759	1806	1856
Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	417	436	454	472	491	509	528	546	564	583	601
	UCL	514	573	622	666	707	746	784	820	855	889	922
	LCL	321	299	286	279	274	272	271	272	274	276	280
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	540	566	593	620	646	673	699	726	753	779	806
	UCL	635	702	759	811	860	908	953	997	1040	1082	1124
	LCL	444	431	427	428	432	438	446	455	465	476	488
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	250	263	275	288	300	313	325	338	350	363	375
	UCL	326	369	405	438	468	497	524	550	575	600	624
	LCL	175	157	145	138	132	129	127	125	125	125	126

Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	2553	2654	2754	2855	2955	3056	3156	3257	3357	3458	3558
	UCL	2958	3226	3455	3664	3860	4046	4226	4401	4570	4736	4899
	LCL	2149	2082	2054	2046	2051	2065	2086	2113	2144	2179	2217
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	299	312	324	336	348	361	373	385	397	410	422
	UCL	352	386	415	441	466	489	512	534	555	576	596
	LCL	247	237	233	231	231	232	234	236	240	243	248
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	322	335	348	361	374	387	400	413	426	438	451
	UCL	367	380	393	407	420	433	446	459	473	486	499
	LCL	276	289	302	314	327	340	353	366	378	391	404
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	905	941	978	1014	1050	1086	1122	1158	1194	1230	1266
	UCL	1016	1053	1090	1126	1163	1200	1236	1273	1310	1346	1383
	LCL	794	830	865	901	936	972	1007	1043	1078	1114	1149
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	626	653	680	707	734	762	789	816	843	870	897
	UCL	758	839	908	971	1029	1084	1137	1188	1238	1286	1334
	LCL	494	467	452	444	440	439	440	443	448	453	460
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	165	172	179	186	193	201	208	215	222	229	236
	UCL	202	224	242	259	275	290	304	318	331	344	357
	LCL	129	121	116	113	112	111	111	112	112	114	115
Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	270	282	293	304	316	327	338	350	361	373	384
	UCL	304	315	327	339	350	362	373	385	396	408	419
	LCL	237	248	259	270	281	293	304	315	326	337	349
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	18993	19784	20574	21365	22155	22945	23736	24526	25316	26107	26897
	UCL	20661	22142	23462	24700	25884	27030	28148	29243	30319	31380	32428
	LCL	17326	17425	17686	18029	18426	18861	19324	19809	20314	20833	21366
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	3346	3507	3667	3828	3988	4149	4309	4470	4630	4791	4951
	UCL	3925	4325	4669	4984	5281	5565	5839	6105	6365	6619	6869
	LCL	2768	2689	2666	2672	2695	2733	2780	2834	2896	2962	3033

Arges-Model_34	Forecast	749	781	812	843	874	906	937	968	999	1031	1062
	UCL	848	920	983	1041	1096	1148	1199	1248	1296	1344	1390
	LCL	650	641	640	645	653	663	675	688	703	718	734
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	228	238	248	258	268	278	288	298	308	318	328
	UCL	271	299	323	345	365	384	403	421	438	455	472
	LCL	185	177	173	171	171	172	173	175	178	181	184
Dâmbovita-Model_36	Forecast	492	520	547	574	602	629	657	684	711	739	766
	UCL	586	653	710	762	812	859	905	950	993	1036	1077
	LCL	398	387	384	387	392	399	408	418	430	442	455
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	187	196	206	215	225	234	244	253	263	272	282
	UCL	223	248	269	289	307	324	341	357	373	388	404
	LCL	150	144	142	142	143	144	147	150	153	156	160
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	220	228	237	246	255	263	272	281	290	298	307
	UCL	278	311	339	363	386	407	427	447	466	484	502
	LCL	161	145	136	129	123	120	117	115	113	113	112
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	1253	1318	1382	1447	1512	1577	1642	1707	1771	1836	1901
	UCL	1475	1631	1767	1891	2008	2120	2228	2334	2437	2538	2637
	LCL	1031	1004	998	1004	1016	1034	1055	1079	1106	1135	1165
Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
	UCL	269	291	309	324	337	349	359	370	379	388	397
	LCL	149	127	110	95	82	70	59	49	39	30	21
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	15597	16178	16758	17338	17919	18499	19080	19660	20240	20821	21401
	UCL	17406	18735	19890	20955	21963	22929	23864	24775	25666	26539	27399
	LCL	13789	13620	13626	13722	13875	14070	14295	14545	14815	15102	15403
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	13637	14084	14532	14980	15428	15875	16323	16771	17219	17666	18114
	UCL	15269	16393	17359	18244	19077	19873	20641	21387	22115	22828	23527
	LCL	12005	11776	11705	11716	11778	11877	12005	12154	12322	12505	12701

Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	1961	2093	2226	2359	2491	2624	2756	2889	3022	3154	3287
	UCL	2177	2399	2600	2791	2974	3153	3328	3500	3670	3838	4004
	LCL	1745	1788	1852	1926	2008	2094	2185	2278	2373	2471	2570
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	5126	5371	5617	5863	6108	6354	6599	6845	7091	7336	7582
	UCL	5541	5959	6337	6694	7038	7372	7699	8021	8338	8651	8961
	LCL	4710	4783	4897	5031	5179	5335	5500	5669	5844	6022	6203
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	1806	1882	1959	2035	2111	2187	2264	2340	2416	2492	2569
	UCL	2045	2123	2200	2278	2355	2432	2510	2587	2665	2742	2820
	LCL	1567	1642	1717	1792	1867	1942	2017	2092	2167	2242	2318
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	730	759	789	818	847	876	905	934	964	993	1022
	UCL	836	910	972	1030	1084	1136	1186	1235	1282	1329	1374
	LCL	624	609	605	605	609	616	624	634	645	657	670
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	309	323	337	351	365	378	392	406	420	434	448
	UCL	349	380	407	431	455	477	499	520	541	562	582
	LCL	269	266	267	270	274	280	286	292	299	307	314
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	171	180	188	197	205	214	222	231	239	248	257
	UCL	207	216	224	233	242	250	259	268	276	285	294
	LCL	136	144	153	161	169	178	186	194	203	211	219
Olt-Model_49	Forecast	238	247	256	266	275	284	293	302	311	321	330
	UCL	271	280	289	299	308	317	327	336	345	355	364
	LCL	205	214	223	232	241	251	260	269	278	287	296
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	331	341	351	361	371	382	392	402	412	422	432
	UCL	373	384	394	404	415	425	435	446	456	466	477
	LCL	289	299	308	318	328	338	348	358	368	378	388
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	3328	3482	3637	3792	3946	4101	4255	4410	4565	4719	4874
	UCL	3752	4082	4372	4640	4895	5140	5378	5610	5838	6061	6281
	LCL	2903	2882	2902	2943	2997	3061	3133	3210	3292	3377	3467

Arad-Model_52	Forecast	640	670	701	731	762	792	823	853	884	914	945
	UCL	756	835	902	964	1022	1077	1130	1182	1233	1282	1331
	LCL	523	506	499	499	502	507	515	524	535	547	559
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169
	UCL	206	222	234	243	252	260	268	274	281	287	293
	LCL	132	116	104	95	86	78	70	64	57	51	45
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	423	440	457	474	490	507	524	541	557	574	591
	UCL	480	497	514	531	548	565	582	599	616	633	650
	LCL	367	383	400	416	433	449	466	482	499	515	531
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	2095	2201	2306	2412	2517	2623	2728	2834	2939	3045	3150
	UCL	2329	2531	2710	2878	3038	3194	3345	3493	3638	3782	3923
	LCL	1862	1871	1903	1946	1996	2052	2112	2174	2240	2308	2377

8. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this scientific article offers a comprehensive statistical overview of the Information and Communication Sector in the Romanian Mountain Region from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to our understanding of the sector's evolution, providing valuable insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers alike. Future research directions and recommendations for sustainable development are also discussed.

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